

Relativistic Dynamics and Energy in R5

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Contents

The kinetic energy of the motion of a body moving in a relativistic manner in four-dimensional space is specified, and the relativistic mass increase is replaced by the increase in four-dimensional velocity. The existence of rest mass and the nature of time are explained.

Sections:

1. Introduction
2. Momentum, Mass, and Energy in Four-Dimensional Space
3. The Invariance of Total Energy and Total Momentum
4. Force and Acceleration
5. Energy, Mass, and Time
6. Summary and Outlook

Attachment

1. Introduction

The hypothesis presented in [1], that relativistically moving bodies move in a four-dimensional auxiliary space, raises the question of whether energy is also associated with the component of motion in the direction of the fourth dimension. Apparently, no energy has yet been measured that occurs in a fourth dimension. On the other hand, the question arises as to whether the increase in mass with velocity contains the answer to the previous question.

In [1], equations (6) and (7)

$$v_w = \frac{v}{c} \cdot v_x^2 \quad (1)$$

and
$$v_x^2 + v_w^2 = v^2 \quad (2)$$

are derived for the velocity component v_w in the direction of the fourth dimension w and for the motion v composed of the components v_w and v_x . (In [1], $v = v'$, since this is also the velocity of the inertial frame S' of the moving body.) Furthermore, according to [1], for the angle ψ at which the body moves relative to the x -axis in the x - w -plane, the following equations (5) hold:

$$\cos \psi = \frac{l}{l'} = \frac{v_x}{v} \quad , \text{ s. Fig. 1}$$

and

$$\cos \psi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2}} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \quad . \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: A rod of length l moves at the relativistic velocity v_x in the positive x -direction. In the assumed four-dimensional auxiliary space, according to [1], its rest length l' , and the velocity v ($= v'$) of its rest frame appear at an angle ψ , and its component v_w in the direction of the fourth dimension w .

2. Momentum, Mass, and Energy in Four-Dimensional Space

The relativistic mass increase is a purely observational phenomenon without a causal explanation and is therefore actually surprising. It is an obvious interpretation of the momentum, which is mathematically too small in the observer's frame when using the rest mass due to time dilation, because otherwise the velocity would have to be greater than the measured velocity.

Based on the conservation of momentum when switching between inertial frames moving relative to one another, a more modern interpretation explains the conservation of momentum through the increase in velocity, not mass:

$$p = m v = (m_0 \gamma) v = m_0 (\gamma v)$$

The mass m_0 is therefore conserved. (One can replace m_0 with m .)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{With } v = v_x \text{ follows } \quad p &= m_0 \frac{1}{\cos \psi} v_x = m_0 \frac{v}{v_x} v_x \\ \mathbf{p} &= m_0 \mathbf{v} \quad (\text{Bold text indicates a vector.}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Accordingly, the four-dimensional velocity v carries the momentum [2]; that is, the velocity is in fact greater than the observed velocity, but only in four-dimensional space. This lends the previously “auxiliary space” a semblance of reality.

Then it is justified to assume that the total energy E and the kinetic energy E_k are also associated with v , and that in three-dimensional space only the perpendicular projection of the velocity occurs.

$$\text{With} \quad E = \gamma m_0 c^2$$

the total kinetic energy of the motion with velocity v is given by

$$E_k = \gamma m_0 c^2 - m_0 c^2 = m_0 c^2 (\gamma - 1) \quad .$$

$$\text{With the kinetic energy in the x-direction} \quad E_{kx} = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v_x^2$$

it follows that the kinetic energy in the w-direction is $E_{kw} = E_k - E_{kx}$,

$$\text{that is} \quad E_{kw} = m_0 c^2 (\gamma - 1) - \frac{1}{2} m_0 v_x^2 \quad . \quad (5)$$

This is the energy of the velocity component in the direction of the fourth dimension w , as sought in the introduction, which leads to an increase in effective velocity .

3. The Invariance of Total Energy and Total Momentum

Since the old interpretation involving variable mass also yields correct results in many cases, we may then also use its formulas

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} = m_0 \gamma \quad , \quad E = m c^2 \quad , \quad E_0 = m_0 c^2 \quad \text{and} \quad E_k = E - E_0$$

as already done above.

$$\text{Let} \quad \gamma = \frac{m}{m_0}$$

$$\text{it follows from (3)} \quad \cos \psi = \frac{m_0}{m}$$

$$\text{and further} \quad \frac{m_0}{m} = \frac{v_x}{v} \quad .$$

$$\text{Expanding in terms of } c^2 \text{ gives} \quad \frac{E_0}{E} = \frac{v_x}{v} \quad , \quad (6)$$

that is, the energies are related to one another in the same way as the corresponding velocities, and therefore form a right-angled triangle in Fig. 2 that is similar to the triangles shown in Fig. 1.

From $\cos \psi = \frac{v_x}{v}$ it follows that $\cos \psi = \frac{E_0}{E}$, so

$$E = E_0 / \cos \psi, \quad (7)$$

which provides further evidence of the possible reality of the fourth dimension. The angle ψ can be constructed from the velocity v_x without calculation; see Attachment.

Fig. 2: The four-dimensional geometric relationship between rest energy E_0 , dynamic energy E and momentum p , as well as dynamic kinetic energy $E_k = E - E_0$

The length of the shorter leg of the red right triangle in Fig. 2 is $|c p|$, where p is the momentum from Eq. 4

$$p = m_0 v = m_0 \gamma v_x .$$

Proof:

In the blue right-angled triangle in Fig. 2, the following holds for the velocities

$$v^2 - v_w^2 = v_x^2 \quad \text{with} \quad v = \frac{v_x}{\cos \psi} = v_x \gamma \quad \text{and Eq. 1 .}$$

$$\Rightarrow v_x^2 \gamma^2 - \frac{\gamma^2}{c^2} v_x^4 = v_x^2 \quad | \cdot \frac{c^4}{v_x^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \gamma^2 c^4 - \gamma^2 v_x^2 c^2 = c^4$$

$$\Rightarrow m_0^2 \gamma^2 c^4 - m_0^2 \gamma^2 v_x^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4$$

$$\Rightarrow (m_0 \gamma c^2)^2 - (m_0 \gamma v_x c)^2 = (m_0 c^2)^2$$

$$\Rightarrow E^2 - (c p)^2 = E_0^2 \quad (8)$$

This is the invariance of total energy and total momentum, as described in the theory of special relativity [2]. The fact that it also follows from this four-dimensional approach demonstrates that it is consistent with SRT and makes the reality of the fourth dimension seem even more likely.

From Eq. 8, we have $E^2 = (m_0 c^2)^2 + (c p)^2$
 and using Eq. 4, $E = \sqrt{m_0^2 c^4 + c^2 m_0^2 v^2}$. (9)

This is the total energy as a function of velocity v in four-dimensional space.

4. Force and Acceleration

In particle accelerators, a force that accelerates the charged particles—in this case, in the x -direction—acts on them, increasing their momentum. The following applies [2]

$$F = \frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{d(m_0 \gamma v_x)}{dt} = m_0 \gamma \frac{dv_x}{dt} + m_0 \frac{d\gamma}{dt} v_x = m_0 \gamma a_x + m_0 (\gamma^3 v_x \frac{a_x}{c^2}) v_x ,$$

so $F = m_0 \gamma a_x (1 + (\frac{v_x \gamma}{c})^2)$ (10)

Solving for a_x , we get $a_x = \frac{F}{m_0 \gamma (1 + (\frac{v_x \gamma}{c})^2)}$. (11)

As $v_x \rightarrow 0$, $\gamma \rightarrow 1$ and $(v_x \gamma)/c \rightarrow 0$. Then, approximately, $a_x = F/m_0$, which is Newton's second law. As the velocity v_x increases, v and γ also increase, and the acceleration decreases. If the force F acts in a linear accelerator 3.2 km long, as in Stanford, then $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$ and thus $a_x \rightarrow 0$, so that the speed limit c cannot be exceeded, as was demonstrated there in 1974.

The speed of light was practically reached after just 1 km. However, the force that continues to act imparts further energy to the electron, which now leads only to the acceleration of v_w and thus to an increase in ψ (see Fig. 3). The particle therefore describes a curve with left-hand curvature in the x - w plane.

For $v_x \rightarrow c$, according to Eq. 3, $\psi \rightarrow 90^\circ$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$,
 and therefore $v_w \rightarrow \infty$ (Eq. 1) and $v \rightarrow \infty$ (Eq. 2).

Fig. 3 illustrates the position of the velocity vectors \mathbf{v} for increasing velocities v_x .

Fig. 3: Increase in velocity v in four-dimensional space and in the angle ψ as the velocity v_x increases in three-dimensional space, shown for $v_x = 0.5c$; $0.8c$; $0.9c$; $0.99c$.

From (1) it follows that
$$v_w = \frac{v_x^2}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_x^2}} . \quad (12)$$

On the corresponding graph, the tips of the vectors \mathbf{v} lie, see Fig. 3 and Attachment.

In the following, the acceleration (for $\mathbf{a} \parallel \mathbf{F}$) in four-dimensional space is derived.

For the four-dimensional acceleration vector, we have

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{\Delta \mathbf{v}}{\Delta t} ,$$

and for the three-dimensional acceleration vector,

$$\mathbf{a}_x = \frac{\Delta v_x}{\Delta t} .$$

For their magnitudes, we have

$$\frac{a}{a_x} = \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta v_x}$$

and thus

$$a = a_x \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta v_x} .$$

Fig. 4: Relativistic acceleration of a particle in four-dimensional space

As $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ and thus also $\Delta v \rightarrow 0$, the secant vector a becomes a tangent vector, and $\Delta v/(\Delta v_x)$ becomes the derivative $dv/(dv_x)$ of $v = \gamma v_x$.

So

$$a = a_x \frac{dv}{dv_x}$$

$$a = a_x \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dv_x} v_x + \gamma \right)$$

$$\frac{d\gamma}{dv_x} = \frac{d}{dv_x} \left(1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = -\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2} \right)^{-\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \left(-\frac{2}{c^2} v_x \right) = \gamma^3 \frac{v_x}{c^2}$$

$$a = a_x \left(\gamma^3 \frac{v_x^2}{c^2} + \gamma \right) = a_x \gamma \left(\gamma^2 \frac{v_x^2}{c^2} + 1 \right) = a_x \gamma \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} + 1 \right)$$

$$\text{Eq. 11} \Rightarrow a = \frac{F}{m_0 \gamma \left(1 + \left(\frac{v_x \gamma}{c} \right)^2 \right)} \gamma \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} + 1 \right) = \frac{F}{m_0 \gamma \left(1 + \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2 \right)} \gamma \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2} + 1 \right)$$

$$a = \frac{F}{m_0} \quad (13)$$

In four-dimensional space, Newton's second law thus also holds for relativistic velocities. This, too, is a result well-known in SRT [2], which in turn confirms the approach used here. It appears to contradict Figures 3 and 4, since in those figures, as v_x approaches c with constant Δv_x increments, the Δv -arrows become increasingly longer, so that Δv_w —and thus a —by no means appears to be constant. However, the times Δt must be taken into account, which increase accordingly as v_x approaches c .

Eq. 8 and 4: $c p = c m_0 v \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{c p}{m_0 c} = v$

This means that the right-angled triangle in Fig. 2, with invariance of total energy and momentum (Eq. 8), corresponds in Fig. 5 to the right-angled triangle formed by the vectors \mathbf{v}_E , \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{c} , with invariance of five-dimensional and four-dimensional velocity.

$$v_E^2 - v^2 = c^2 \quad (14)$$

Hereat, $v > c$ may apply, but $v_E \geq c$ always applies.

The terms for the total energy $E = m_0 c \sqrt{c^2 + v^2}$ and $E = m c^2$ are equivalent.

Proof: $m_0 c^2 \sqrt{\frac{c^2 + v^2}{c^2}} = m_0 \gamma c^2$

$$\sqrt{1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = \gamma \quad (15)$$

$$v = \gamma v_x \quad \Rightarrow \quad 1 + \left(\frac{\gamma v_x}{c}\right)^2 = \gamma^2$$

$$1 = \gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2}\right)$$

$$1 = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2}} \left(1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2}\right)$$

$$1 = 1 \quad \text{q. e. d.}$$

Since $\frac{c}{c} \sqrt{c^2 + v^2} = c \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}$

it follows that $E = m_0 c \sqrt{c^2 + v^2} = m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}$

$$E = E_0 \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \quad (16)$$

It follows that the total kinetic energy is

$$E_k = E - E_0 = E_0 \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} - 1\right) \quad (17)$$

See Fig. 6 for the graphs $E(v)$ and $E_k(v)$. As can be seen in Eq. 8, these are hyperbola branches.

The expression for total kinetic energy from Section 2 $E_k = m_0 c^2 (\gamma - 1)$

is equivalent to that in Eq. 17, since $\sqrt{1 + v^2/c^2} = \gamma$, see Eq. 15.

Fig. 6: Plots of the graphs of $E = E_0 \sqrt{1+(v/c)^2}$; $D = [0 ; \infty[$ (red) with its asymptote $E/(m_0 c^2) = v/c$ and $E_k = m_0 c^2 (\sqrt{1+(v/c)^2} - 1)$; $D = [0 ; \infty[$ (black) with $E_0 = 1 \text{ Nm}$; Unlike v_x , v is unbounded; see Fig. 3.

The kinetic energy of a particle moving at relativistic speeds is given by

$$E_k = E - E_0 = m c^2 - m_0 c^2 = (m - m_0) c^2 = \Delta m c^2$$

$$(9) \Rightarrow \Delta m = \frac{E - E_0}{c^2} = \frac{m_0 c v_E - m_0 c^2}{c^2}$$

$$\Delta m = \frac{m_0}{c} (v_E - c) \quad (18)$$

The supposed relativistic mass increase Δm is therefore a linear function of the five-dimensional velocity v_E and proportional to the velocity difference $v_E - c$ (see Fig. 7). According to this hypothesis, it is thus the kinetic energy of this velocity difference (divided by c^2). In the relativistic mass increase, the velocity v_E makes itself felt, even though it lies in five-dimensional space. And this relationship also serves as an indication of the claimed motion of our three-dimensional space at the speed of light through a five-dimensional space.

Fig. 7: Illustration of the difference between the magnitudes of v and c , $v_E - c$, to which the relativistic mass increase is proportional. For $v_x \rightarrow c$, $v \rightarrow \infty$ and $v_E \rightarrow \infty$. Since the subtrahend c , the distance with magnitude c , remains constant, $v_E - c$ also approaches infinity, just like the relativistic mass increase.

Δm can also be expressed in terms of the four-velocity v . From Eq. 17, we obtain

$$\Delta m = \frac{E - E_0}{c^2} = \frac{E_0}{c^2} \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} - 1 \right),$$

which, together with Eq. 15, leads to the well-known formula $\Delta m = \frac{E_0}{c^2} (\gamma - 1)$.

6. Summary and Outlook

The five-dimensional velocity of a body moving at a relativistic speed possesses the kinetic energy that was initially interpreted as a dynamic relativistic mass. But its mass remains constant. The assumed relativistic increase in mass can be explained by the fact that three-dimensional velocity is limited by the speed of light, which forces an increase in four-dimensional velocity and its kinetic energy.

A momentum is associated with the body's four-dimensional velocity, and the relativistic energy-momentum invariant is derived from the arrangement of the three-dimensional and four-dimensional velocities.

It is shown that Newton's second law applies to the acceleration of the four-dimensional velocity.

The total energy is represented mathematically and graphically as a function of the four-dimensional velocity.

The rest energy of a body is the kinetic energy of its motion through the time dimension. Because mass is constant thus the nature of all mass is explained as this kinetic energy.

The four-dimensional cosmos—and with it the three-dimensional universe—moves at the speed of light orthogonally through the fifth, timelike dimension. Time thereby acquires a spatial character. Accordingly, the universe is a moving three-dimensional cross-section of five-dimensional spacetime.

Time is the variable spatial coordinate of the four-dimensional cross-section of a five-dimensional Euclidean space, which consists of the three-dimensional universe plus a fourth, spatial dimension, and moves at the speed of light perpendicular to all four directions of propagation in the fifth dimension.

The supplementation of the previous [1] four-dimensional relativistic kinematics by the presented statements on dynamics and energy not only closes a gap in our understanding but also explains the constancy of mass, the energy-momentum invariance, the existence of rest energy and the essence of mass and time. This may serve as further evidence that the hypothetical fourth spatial dimension is not merely a mathematical construct but could actually exist. And this approach presumably also explains why the speed of light sets the upper limit for all speeds of action.

References

[1] www.zenodo.org ; DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17266293
www.roland-sprenger.de: Rest length and time in five-dimensional spacetime

[2] [en.wikipedia.org/Mass in special relativity](http://en.wikipedia.org/Mass_in_special_relativity)

Attachment

Derivation of ψ

From Eq. 3,
$$\cos \psi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_x^2}{c^2}}$$

it follows that
$$\cos^2 \psi + \frac{v_x^2}{c^2} = 1$$

and from this
$$\sin \psi = \frac{v_x}{c} .$$

If one draws a circle of radius $1c$ centered at the origin and draws a line parallel to the v_x - axis at a distance of v_x/c (see Fig. 7), the free leg of ψ points through the intersection of the parallel line with the arc of the circle.

Fig. 7: Construction method for the angle ψ using only the velocity v_x

Function $v_w (v_x)$

$$v_w = \frac{\gamma}{c} \cdot v_x^2 = \frac{v_x^2}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_x^2}}$$

